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of **EXPRESSION**
A Creative Folio

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Promise of Healing

Every day the sun rises,
Like the storm wave ashore arises.
“Don’t be afraid is what they whisper,
“Be brave and take the step towards wonders.”

I try every single day,
But why does the pain never fade?
Why do the hunting dreams creep?
Perilously wound my heart and brain.

I close my eyes and pray,
wishing to forget the pain.
But in every breath I take,
The killing ache remains.

As I walk through the darkness,
The hope inside my chest fades.
Due to wounds that tire my system,
Should I still fight and do my best?

For tomorrow, in every sunrise I vow,
As I peek at the rising waves
As I stare blankly at the silhouette of cries
A promise that healing will come somehow